

Garret chats about the Rosehill Cemetery Story from 1988
by Garret Thomas Kaess

“Hey bro

That cemetery story from 1988 was the real deal I'm not lying. It was like phantasm with midget dwarfs poppin up from behind gravestones and shit and both me and Jon go, " Oooohhhhhhhhh!!!" Ha ha!!then we ran for our lives! With some guy with a shovel not far behind! Lol

Ain't no joke lol
Garret”

“Hey bro

What was so freaky about that rosehill incident was that it was really dark and a full moon so the moonlight lit up the tops of the gravestones not far from the little pond and as I was looking at one I thought I saw a shadow move then I said to John did you see that? Then all of a sudden a midget head popped up in some dark robe and both me and John freaked out," oooohhhhhhhhhhh!" And flight took over. As we were running deeper into rosehill we saw a tall guy looked like the undertaker with a shovel cussing up a storm try to converge on us from about 50 yards away at which point we hid in the forest very deep and quiet as this guy was scanning the trees looking for us. Finally he gave up and we jumped the fence out of that place on the corner of Western and brynmawr. No bs story totally real shit!

Shit was freaked out! Lol
Garret”

Brian replies: “Dude! All you missing was the roaming ball from *Phantasm!*”

So, these things claimed by Garret & John were the ‘things seen, or things believed in a moment of terror,’ as similarly related by Tacitus concerning the Romans in Germania.